

Universität Potsdam

Consent form for Notetaking for the PROTEST-AIRT project

Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Fellowship (Grant Agreement 101057156)

I hereby consent to and authorize the University of Potsdam, a non-profit academic institution, to produce and store written notes about my conversation with Dr Alexander Araya López for the PROTEST-AIRT project. This project analyses the emerging dissent against air transport in Europe and the notes could be used **in anonymized form** for both academic and communication purposes (for example, in public lectures, media or the official website of the project).

I authorize Dr Alexander Araya López, the researcher in charge of the PROTEST-AIRT project, to contact me at a later date for any clarification or for requesting a more formal participation in this study.

YES

NO

- **You must be 18 years of age or older to take part in this research study.**
- **You will be given a copy of this consent form for your records.**

Name:

Address:

Email:

Date:

Signature:

Dr Alexander ARAYA LÓPEZ
Sociologist and Marie S.-Curie Postdoctoral Fellow (2022-2024)
Project PROTEST-AIRT
Universität Potsdam
Email: [\[ADD EMAIL\]](#)